

Engaging Pearl and Rubin to Teach Causality in Statistics Classrooms

Chris Rhoads, University of Connecticut, Storrs, CT

Abstract: The importance of causal inference to the field of statistics suggests that the topic should be covered in an introductory or intermediate level class. However, there is not much guidance available regarding how to teach causal inference to students with a limited background in statistics. The current paper makes some suggestions for how to accomplish this goal. It recommends teaching two of the most important frameworks for exploring causal inference: Rubin's Causal Model and Pearl's Directed Acyclic Graphs. Exploring the similarities and differences between the two frameworks allows important points about causal inference to come to the fore.

Keywords: Statistical Education, Rubin's Causal Model, Directed Acyclic Graphs, Causal Inference.

Introduction

There was a time when statisticians denied that their profession had anything to do with understanding causation. Holland opens his seminal 1986 paper, *Statistics and Causal Inference*, by acknowledging this fact, stating, "The reaction of many statisticians when confronted with the possibility that their profession might contribute to a discussion of causation is immediately to deny that there is any such possibility" (Holland, 1986). Pearl and Mackenzie (2018; Chapter 2) argue that the aversion of statisticians to causal questions stems from Karl Pearson and quote one of Pearson's students as follows, "To contrast 'causation' and 'correlation' is unwarranted because causation is simply perfect correlation" (Niles, 1923).

It has been almost forty years since Holland's paper and much has changed. There are at least two full journals devoted almost exclusively to causal inference: *Journal of Causal Inference* and *Observational Studies*. A quick search of the conference program for the 2025 Joint Statistical Meetings suggests no less than 94 papers will be presented on the topic.

Despite these advances, statistical educators have struggled to understand how and when to integrate teaching about causal inference into the statistics curriculum. Its importance to the field suggests that it should receive some treatment in introductory statistics classes. However, introductory courses rarely pay much attention to causal inference (Cummiskey et. al, 2020). Recent papers have sought to change this situation by providing suggestions for how causal inference topics might be integrated into the introductory statistics curriculum (Cummiskey and Lubke, 2022; Cummiskey et al., 2020).

Two Frameworks for Understanding Causal Inference

This paper advocates for teaching causal inference through the lens of two of the most important frameworks for thinking about the topic: Rubin's Causal Model (RCM) and Pearl's Directed Acyclic graphs (DAGs). It argues that there is particular value in being able to compare and contrast the frameworks. That is, both frameworks should be taught. This may be difficult to accomplish if only a week or two are available in the context of a traditional

introductory statistics class. However, it should be very possible in the context of a more modern class focused on statistical literacy (e.g, Schield, 2023).

While both frameworks should be taught, any instructor must make a choice about which framework will be presented first. Whichever one is presented first will end up becoming the primary framework for thinking about causality in the class. Mainly due to my own comfort with the RCM approach, I will focus on beginning with this approach. However, I will also review the potential advantages of beginning with the DAG approach

Using Rubin’s Causal Model as the Primary Approach

Beginning with RCM allows the instructor to focus attention on the idea of potential outcomes. Potential outcomes are intuitive even to beginners, and they provide the opportunity to illustrate important and sometimes unexpected truths about causal investigations.

RCM postulates that quantitative investigations of cause and effect necessarily involve the comparison of one potential state of the world (Cause 1) to a different potential state of the world (Cause 0). In other words, causal comparisons are always relative comparisons. We cannot evaluate the claim, *Sue got a good job because she went to college*, without specifying what Sue would have done if she hadn't gone to college.

The recognition of a causal investigation as a comparison between two different potential states leads to the definition of a causal effect in terms of potential outcomes. Given some outcome of interest, y , and a particular time of measurement, t , the causal effect of “1” relative to “0” for individual i in the population is defined as:

$$y_{it}(1)-y_{it}(0) \tag{1}$$

Equation (1) makes very clear what Holland (1986) calls “The Fundamental Problem of Causal Inference”. The problem is that we can never observe the same individual under both cause “1” and cause “0” at the same time. Half of the information that we need to discover the causal effect for an individual is always missing.

With only this very limited machinery it is possible to illustrate profound truths about the nature of causal inference. The first few insights follow immediately from a careful examination of equation (1) and begin to show the ways that causal inference differs from population inference¹. Imagine we want to learn the average income of every citizen of the United States at a particular point in time. We can do so through taking a random sample of citizens. If we take a large enough random sample, we can know the true average income to any degree of precision we desire. Of course there are operational difficulties in obtaining a truly random sample. However, in principle the answer can be known based only on the data collected in the study.

¹ Population inference is defined in Schield (2024) as “making inferences about a population based on information obtained from a sample of that population”.

The same is not true in causal investigations. Additional qualitative assumptions are necessary. Students are sometimes surprised to learn that this is true even for randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

The initial assumptions that are needed to bring coherence to equation (1) have been dubbed SUTVA (Stable Unit Treatment Value) in the literature. SUTVA has two parts. The first part states that there must be only one version of treatment. Consider our question about the effect of Sue's college attendance on her job quality. Suppose we have some scale available to measure job quality. In truth there are multiple colleges that Sue could have attended and multiple alternative paths she could have pursued had she not attended college. These are each potential versions of treatment. If these different versions lead to different numerical quantities for $y_{it}(1)$ or $y_{it}(0)$ in equation (1) then equation (1) is not well defined and SUTVA is violated.

Alternatively, suppose that the quality of the job Sue would obtain after college would be different depending on whether her best friend does or does not attend college with her. In this case the second part of SUTVA is violated. This type of SUTVA violation again implies that different possible states of the world lead to different numerical quantities for $y_{it}(1)$ or $y_{it}(0)$ and so causal effects cannot be defined. There is no analogous definitional problem when the goal is population inference about U.S. average income from a sample. Causal inference requires much more effort to even define the problem.

Potential outcomes allow for an easy illustration of some surprising limitations to RCTs. The fundamental problem of causal inference makes it impossible to learn about causal effects for individuals except in very rare cases where strong assumptions are plausible. The randomized controlled trial gives up on trying to learn about individual causal effects and instead seeks to estimate the average causal effect for a population. The averaging process is more important than it might seem at first glance. When estimating incomes in the US from a random sample we could just as easily seek to estimate the median or a percentile instead of an average. The same is not true for causal effects. Median causal effects cannot be determined by an RCT. This can be illustrated from a simple example that leverages potential outcomes.

Example 1: Median Causal Effects

Consider table 1, which lists potential outcomes of four individuals who are part of a hypothetical study of college going. The quality of their jobs after attending (or not attending) college are rated on a scale of 1-10 and listed in the table.

Table 1: Potential outcomes for a hypothetical study of college going.

Unit	$Y_i(1)$: College	$Y_i(0)$: No College	Causal effect
1	4	3	1

2	5	5	0
3	6	4	2
4	9	4	5
Avg	6	4	2
Median	5.5	4	2

A randomized experiment will allow us to correctly (ie. without bias) estimate the average potential outcome in the college condition from the average observed outcomes of those assigned to the college condition. Similarly, we can estimate the average potential outcome in the non-college condition from the average observed outcomes of those assigned to the non-college condition. The average causal effect is easily obtained by subtracting the second estimate from the first.

The process described in the previous paragraph works only because averaging is a linear operation. However, obtaining the median is not a linear operation. The table clearly shows that there is no way to obtain the median causal effect from the medians obtained in the groups randomly assigned to the different conditions. If desired, the identification of the average causal effect and the non-identification of the median causal effect can be illustrated in more detail by mimicking table 3, which is part of the next example.

Example 2: Conditioning on a pretest.

For students who have learned about the concepts of “bias” and “regression adjustment”, we can use potential outcomes to show that adjusting for a pretest score in an RCT can lead to a biased estimate (but will tend to increase precision).

Table 2: Adding a pretest to the previous example

Unit	Yi(1): College	Yi(0): No College	Causal effect	Pretest
1	4	3	1	2
2	5	5	0	5
3	6	4	2	5
4	9	4	5	8
Avg	6	4	2	5

Table 2 is a reproduction of table 1 with a pre-test added. Table 3 lists all possible outcomes from randomizing the units in table 2, along with summary quantities that could be computed for each randomization. To understand the example students must know that an adjusted mean is equal to the unadjusted mean minus the regression coefficient times the average value of the X variable for which adjustment is being made (i.e. the adjusted mean is $\bar{Y} - \hat{\beta}\bar{X}$). They also must understand that bias is defined as the difference between the average value of the estimate across all possible randomizations and the true value of the parameter. Armed only with these two facts, it is easy to see from the table that: (a) the unadjusted treatment effect estimate is unbiased (bottom of column 9) and (b) the adjusted treatment effect estimate has a downward bias (bottom of column 10).

Class discussion should note that the reason for the bias is because the pretest for unit 4 is much closer to the college potential outcome than the non-college potential outcome, but the same is not true for the other units. Furthermore, the pretest is particularly large for unit 4. As a result, the observed regression coefficient is much larger whenever unit 4 is in the treatment group. The larger estimated regression coefficient results in a larger adjustment, dampening the estimate of the treatment effect. The conclusion is that bias in causal studies can come from unexpected sources, even in RCTs.

This example also provides the opportunity for a side discussion on the topic of bias-variance tradeoffs, which arise frequently in statistics. While the adjusted treatment effect estimate does have a downwards bias, it is also less variable. The estimated value is never more than 1 unit from the truth. On the other hand, two-thirds of the time the unadjusted estimate is more than 1 unit from the truth.

Table 3: Possible outcomes from randomizing the units in Table 2.

<i>Units Rand to Coll</i>	<i>Obs Coll Avg</i>	<i>Obs no-Coll Avg</i>	<i>Obs Avg Coll Pretest</i>	<i>Obs Avg no-Coll Pretest</i>	<i>Obs reg coeff</i>	<i>Adj mean Coll</i>	<i>Adj mean no-coll</i>	<i>Unadj t effect est.</i>	<i>Adjust effect est</i>
1,2	4.5	4.0	3.5	6.5	0.17	3.90	2.89	0.50	1.01
1,3	5	4.5	3.5	6.5	0.17	4.40	3.39	0.50	1.01
1,4	6.5	4.5	5.0	5.0	0.83	2.35	0.35	2.00	2.00
2,3	5.5	3.5	5.0	5.0	0.17	4.65	2.65	2.00	2.00
2,4	7.0	3.5	6.5	6.5	0.83	1.60	0.59	3.50	1.01
3,4	7.5	4.0	6.5	6.5	0.83	2.10	1.09	3.50	1.01
Avg	6.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	3.17	1.83	2.00	1.34

Example 3: Bias in Observational studies and the ATT/ATE distinction

A final example that leverages potential outcomes introduces the important idea of confounding and the distinction between different types of average causal effects. Table 4 augments table 3 with an additional column that denotes whether an individual would choose to attend college if given the option. Table 4 allows us to illustrate two key additional points about causal inference by using potential outcomes.

First, we notice that, among individuals who choose to attend college the true average causal effect of college attendance is $(5+0)/2$ or 2.5. However, the average among those who do not choose to attend college is $(2+1)/2$ or 1.5. The average among all individuals is the average of 2.5 and 1.5, which is 2. The literature has a name for these different causal effects. The first one is known as the Average treatment effect for the treated (ATT), the second as the average treatment effect for the non-treated (ATNT), and the last as the average treatment effect for the experiment (ATE). In short, the true causal effect is different for those who choose college. This finding should not be surprising. Perhaps those who choose college do so because they understand that they are particularly well situated to take advantage of the benefits that college can offer.

Second, we notice that, unlike a randomized experiment, we are now not able to obtain an unbiased estimate of the true average causal effect. If we compare the average outcomes of those who attend college to the average outcomes of those who do not, we will see that the comparison gives us an estimate of $(9+5)/2 = 7$ minus $(4+3)/2 = 3.5$, or 3.5. Notice that this is not a good estimate of any of the average causal effects defined in the previous paragraph.

Examining the table, it is easy to tell a story about what went wrong. Individuals with higher pretests were more likely to choose to go to college. Furthermore, individuals with higher pretests tend to have higher potential outcomes under both conditions. Thus, the pretest functions as a confounding variable. Understanding the need to account for confounding variables is, of course, one of the most important topics in causal inference.

One way to attempt to account for confounding variables is to use regression adjustment. However, example 2 has already shown that regression adjustment can fail to produce unbiased estimates, even in RCTs. Presented next to each other, example 2 and example 3 illustrate the need to consider multiple ways to adjust for confounding and can therefore be a jumping off point for a discussion of more advanced techniques like propensity scores.

Table 4: Observational study where individuals choose to attend college.

Unit	$Y_i(1)$: College	$Y_i(0)$: No College	Causal effect	Pretest	Individual chooses
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1	4	3	1	2	No college
2	5	5	0	5	College
3	6	4	2	5	No College
4	9	4	5	8	College
Avg	6	4	2	5	

Using Pearl's Directed Acyclic Graphs as the primary approach

The existing literature has noted that it may instead be preferable to use Pearl's DAGs as the primary approach to introduce causal inference to a novice audience (Cumiskey and Lubke, 2022; Cumiskey et al., 2020). The rationale for preferring the DAG approach is that it allows for the presentation of important ideas like confounding using easy to understand graphs.

An example of a DAG illustrating the confounding problem is provided as figure 1. The DAG illustrates that IQ is a possible confounding variable when trying to estimate the causal effect of college on job quality.

Figure 1: IQ as confounder of relationship between college and job quality.

Of course, this DAG is a gross oversimplification. To draw a causal DAG that would help solve the problem at hand it would be necessary to include many more variables. The objective is to use qualitative knowledge of known causal relationships to exhaustively list all variables that cause the exposure, the outcome, or some other variable in the model. If all such variables are

listed and the causal relationships are correctly specified, then the researcher can use rules published by Pearl (2009) to know precisely which variables must be measured (and conditioned on) in order to allow for unbiased causal inference.

The primary virtue of the DAG based approach is its focus on identification and the separation of the identification problem from the estimation problem. Most areas of statistics focus on estimation. As such “testing assumptions” involves graphical or numerical displays of observable quantities like model residuals. The DAG based approach makes clear that the most important thing for causal inference is not what you do with the data you have (i.e. your statistical model) but instead ensuring that your research design gives you the data you need (i.e. you must measure all relevant confounders if you aim to identify causal effects using the most common, “back door”, criterion; Pearl, 2009).

A full exposition of the DAG approach is beyond the scope of this paper. A short introduction can be found in Elwert (2013).

Supplementing the primary approach with the other framework and encouraging debate

I have stated earlier that I believe both the DAG and RCM Frameworks should be taught in an introductory course on statistical literacy. Whichever framework is treated as primary, valuable insights can be gleaned by supplementing the primary approach. Furthermore, where the two approaches make different recommendations, vigorous debate can ensue. Such a debate makes statistics come alive for students who are often not mathematically inclined. Unlike classes in social sciences, students may not be used to engaging in debate during statistics class. However, encouraging debate makes statistics seem less like a staid exercise in mathematical computations and more like what it should be: A lively investigation of reality through quantitative models.

Using the DAG framework to supplement RCM based presentation of Causal Inference

First, I consider using the DAG framework to supplement an RCM presentation causal inference. A class focused on RCM will almost certainly devote a fair amount of time to propensity score-based methods. As such, students will learn the importance of checking for covariate balance between the treatment and control group after propensity score-based adjustments have been made (Rubin, 2001). They will also learn that different methods for utilizing propensity scores (e.g. stratification, weighting, matching) will lead to different balance tables (Stuart, 2010).

Often a particular propensity score method will result in less than desirable balance for a particular variable. A common mistake in this case is for the student to remove the variable in question from the analysis. Of course, this makes it appear as though valid causal inference is possible. However, this is just an illusion. Removing the offending variable is exactly the wrong thing to do from the standpoint of causal inference. Refusing to check for balance on a particular variable does not remove its confounding effects. By focusing attention on the need to adjust for

all possible confounding variables, exposure to DAGs can help students schooled in the RCM approach avoid this mistake.

Even students who would not make this mistake can benefit from exposure to the DAG approach. When different approaches lead to different balance tables, students are often at a loss to decide which approach to prefer. Exposure to DAGs makes clear that we should be willing to sacrifice balance on variables we think are unlikely to be confounders (or at least unlikely to be strong confounders) in order to achieve better balance on variables we believe ARE likely to be strong confounders.

Using the RCM framework to supplement DAG based presentation of Causal Inference

The graphical models used in Pearl's DAG approach tend to miss some of the nuances involved in causal inference. For instance, the previous discussion has noted how important averaging is for most approaches to cause-and-effect studies. Because of the Fundamental Problem of Causal Inference, we must give up on measuring individual causal effects and instead content ourselves with average causal effects. However, often averages can be deceptive. They can mislead policymakers when treatment effects are heterogeneous. For this reason, there is rapidly developing literature on the need to think about treatment effect heterogeneity (e.g., Athey & Imbens, 2016; Bryan et al., 2021)

DAGs encourage focusing on identification of a single average causal effect of interest. As such it can be easy to miss opportunities to think about heterogeneity of causal effects. Exposure to RCM and potential outcomes can help by focusing attention on the difference between the ATE and the ATT.

Additionally, the DAG approach tends to view causal relationships as stationary. That is, the role of time is ignored. However, failing to think about the timing of measurement can lead to large errors in causal inference. The same variable that should be treated as a confounder when measured prior to treatment onset should often be treated as a mediator when measured after treatment onset. In the first case, quantitative adjustment via regression or propensity scores is to be desired. In the second case, adjustment is to be avoided. RCM draws attention to the timing of measurement and so helps students primarily versed in Pearl's DAG approach avoid incorrectly adjusting for a mediator or vice versa.

Getting to know both approaches better via debate

While the RCM and DAG approaches to causal inference are usually complementary, Rubin and Pearl have divergent opinions with respect to at least one important question for observational causal inference. Rubin (2007) believes that it is best to use propensity scores to attempt to balance the treatment and control groups with respect to all possible pre-treatment covariates. Pearl (2009b) disagrees, arguing that it is best to not adjust for pre-treatment covariates that might have a so-called "M-structure". Ding and Miratrix (2015) comment on the relative merits of each side of the debate.

There is no space in the current paper to delve into the details of the disagreement. However, familiarizing students with the nature of the disagreement and asking them to take one or the other side in a debate-like format has been a very productive activity in my causal inference focused classes. The research necessary to hone arguments for the debate (and the desire to win) helps students deepen their understanding of the most important questions that statisticians face when engaging in observational causal inference.

Discussion

This paper has shown how two distinct causal inference frameworks, Rubin's Causal Model (RCM) and Pearl's Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), can help teach causal inference to introductory and intermediate statistics students. While the previous section emphasized one area disagreement between Rubin and Pearl, there are many important commonalities. Both frameworks emphasize that identification takes priority over estimation. That is, before estimating a statistical model we must first understand what type of causal effect we are estimating and map out what knowledge we already have about potential confounding variables. This makes clear that measurement takes priority over modeling. I explain this idea in more detail below.

When engaging in observational causal inference it is necessary to account for confounding variables. This task has two distinct parts. First, we must obtain high quality measurements of the potential confounding variables. Call this "the measurement problem". Second, we need a statistical technique that allows us to appropriately account for the measures that have been obtained. Call this "the statistical modeling problem". Generally speaking, the measurement problem is far more important than the statistical modeling problem. That is, if we have obtained measures of the appropriate things, only marginal improvements are available above and beyond (eg.) standard regression. However, if we do not have measures of the appropriate things, even the most cleverly designed statistical technique will not fix the problem.

Pearl's directed acyclic graphs are almost exclusively interested in measurement problems. Rubin's theory can contribute to both parts, as it encourages us to both think about the assignment mechanism and how to make it ignorable (the measurement problem) and it also motivates techniques for accounting for observed variables (e.g. propensity scores).

By comparing and contrasting the way in which Pearl and Rubin approach the confounding problem, students are encouraged to: (a) distinguish between the measurement problem and the statistical modeling problem, (b) understand the primacy of the measurement problem and (c) think about the appropriateness of different ways of accounting for confounding variables. In the end, engaging with both Pearl and Rubin shows the wisdom of the following quote from Light, Singer and Willett (1990), "you can't fix by analysis what you bungled by design."

References

- Athey, S. & Imbens, G. (2016). Recursive partitioning for heterogeneous causal effects. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(27), 7353–7360.
- Bryan, C. J., Tipton, E., & Yeager, D. S. (2021). Behavioural science is unlikely to change the world without a heterogeneity revolution. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 5, 980–989.
- Carver, R., Everson, M., Gabrosek, J., Horton, N., Lock, R., Mocko, M., Rossman, A., Rowell, G., Velleman, P., Witmer, J., and Wood, B. (2016), “*Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education: College Report 2016*,” American Statistical Association.
- Cummiskey, K., Adams, B., Pleuss, J., Turner, D., Clark, N. & Watts, K. (2020) Causal Inference in Introductory Statistics Courses, *Journal of Statistics Education*, 28:1, 2-8, DOI: 10.1080/10691898.2020.1713936
- Cummiskey, K. and Lubke, K (2022). Causality in Statistics and Data Science Education. *AStA Wirtschafts- und Sozialstatistisches Archiv* 16:277–286.
- Ding, P., & Miratrix, L. W. (2015). To adjust or not to adjust? Sensitivity analysis of M-bias and butterfly-bias. *Journal of Causal Inference*, 3(1), 41–57. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jci-2013-0021>
- Elwert, F. (2013). Graphical causal models. In J. H. Morgan & C. Winship (Eds.), *Handbook of causal analysis for social research* (pp. 245–273). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6094-3_12
- Holland, P. (1986) Statistics and Causal Inference. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*.
- Light, R. J., Singer, J. D., & Willett, J. B. (1990). *By design: Planning research on higher education*. Harvard University Press.
- Niles, H. E. (1923). The method of path coefficients—An answer to Wright. *Genetics*, 8(3), 256–260. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/8.3.256>
- Pearl J. (2009a). *Causality: Models, reasoning and inference*, 2nd edn. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Pearl, J. (2009b). Remarks on the method of propensity score. *Statistics in Medicine*, 28(9), 1415–1416. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.3521>
- Pearl, J., and Mackenzie, D. (2018), *The Book of Why: The New Science of Cause and Effect*, New York: Basic Books.
- Rubin D.B. (1974). Estimating causal effects of treatments in randomized and non-randomized studies. *Journal of Educational Psychology* 66, 688–701.

Rubin, D. B. (2001). Using propensity scores to help design observational studies: Application to the tobacco litigation. *Health Services and Outcomes Research Methodology*, 2(3–4), 169–188. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020363010465>

Rubin, D. B. (2007). The design versus the analysis of observational studies for causal effects: Parallels with the design of randomized trials. *Statistics in Medicine*, 26(1), 20–36. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.2739>

Schild, M. (2023). *Statistical Literacy: Critical Thinking about Everyday Statistics*. Kendall-Hunt. <https://he.kendallhunt.com/product/statistical-literacy-2023-critical-thinking-about-everyday-statistics>

Schild (2024). *Statistical Literacy: A New Course*. Retrieved from <https://www.statlit.org/pdf/2024-Schild-ISLP.pdf> May 29, 2025.

Stuart, E. A. (2010). Matching methods for causal inference: A review and a look forward. *Statistical Science*, 25(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1214/09-STS313>